

Effect of the Burnout Syndrome on Intrapreneurship: A Practice in Province Ankara

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Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between both authors. Authors AE and GŞ designed the study, performed the statistical analysis, wrote the protocol and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. Authors AE and GŞ managed the analyses of the study. Authors AE and GŞ managed the literature searches. Both authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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ABSTRACT

In this study identifying the relation between burnout and intrapreneurship was aimed. Additionally, the aim was to reveal the difference between the demographic features and burnout and intrapreneurship. In accordance with this purpose the problem question was identified as "Has the burnout that the employees come through effect their intrapreneurship behaviors. The universe of the study has been chosen from 99 nurses with a convenience sampling method working in a state hospital functioning in Turkey. A face to face questionnaire method has been conducted to the nurses. In the analysis of the data T-test, ANOVA test, regression analysis and correlation analysis was used. According to the results, there is a reverse relation between burnout and intrapreneurship, and came out to a result that a rise in the burnout will have a decrease in the intrapreneurship.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Global competition causes radical changes in all sectors and businesses. Businesses are redefining their strategies by investigating their objectives under these competitive circumstances. Businesses are restructuring their activities against rapid changes in their environment in a radical and meaningful manner with a constant understanding of innovation. Literature suggests “entrepreneurship” as a method for innovation to businesses.

It is argued that entrepreneurship has been designed as a process by which businesses can effectively cope with the realities of competition they can face in facilitating continuous innovation efforts and competing in global markets. It is therefore understood that entrepreneurial attitudes and behaviors are necessary for all size of firms to succeed and grow in competitive environments [1]. Entrepreneurship emphasizes the inoculation of entrepreneurial spirit to everyone in the business. It is stated that the spirit of entrepreneurship created in the enterprise may overcome the resistance of the superstructure against the formation of flexible structures, growth and differentiation [2].

Entrepreneurship is playing an important role in today's economic systems acting with the motives of continuous self-perpetuation and improvement and its importance is gradually increasing in the present world based on competition. The entrepreneurship which falls into the subjects that are mostly examined in the management and economy literature for this importance has been added to classical production factors (labor, capital and natural resources) as the fourth production factor by French economist J.B. Say [3]. It is seen that one of the concepts whose importance is increasing in recent times in terms of organizations is entrepreneurship both out of the organization and within the organization; employees having intrapreneurship qualification are playing critical role in the modification and development of the organizations [4]. The concept of burnout has revealed as an undesired factor for the organizations in this modification and development process of organizations. In this study, burnout and intrapreneurship concepts will be discussed together.

2. LITARURE REVIEW

2.1 The Burnout Concept

The burnout concept was firstly used by Freudenberger in order to express the exhaustion observed in voluntary personnel in health field [5]. Afterwards, Maslach and Jackson defined the burnout as a physical, emotional and mental burnout syndrome which becomes evident with chronic fatigue, desperation and despair feelings, development of a negative self-concept, negative attitudes against profession, life and other people generally [5].

Burnout leads to feelings and behaviors such as loss of motivation, performance decrease, absenteeism, frequent resting or getting permission and even walking off the job in the employees as an undesired factor for the organization [6]. Burnout is a physical, emotional and mental state which is different from the pure exhaustion, wearing and job dissatisfaction; includes physical exhaustion, desperation and despair feelings, negative personality development, inefficiency and negative attitudes against other people [7].

When databases are scanned, it is seen that studies specifically over the burnout for the last 20 years have started to increase expeditiously. Of the burnout studies started in the mid of 1970's, more than 5500 studies have been published until today. It was focused on descriptive and cross sectional studies from 1980's to the mid of 1990's, longitudinal studies came to the fore as from the second half of 1990's [8,9]. Studies over burnout in Turkey were started in 1992. Besides, the study conducted by Ergin in 1992 is important because of being at national level, including all health occupational groups and all regions, being the first and only study conducted with a large sampling. In this study, it was stated that physicians and particularly nurses are the most risky group in terms of burnout within healthcare professionals [10,11].

The most common sizing regarding the burnout was performed by Maslach et al., and dimensions or phases mentioned on this framework are expressed as emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and reduced personal accomplishment feeling. Emotional

exhaustion defines exhaustion of emotional resources of the individual and reduced energy. Employees experiencing emotional exhaustion cannot focus on their works. The individual who experiences the emotional exhaustion uses escape way for reducing his emotional burden and minimizes his correlations with other persons in order to perform the work. Also, categorizing the people in his/her mind, treating to the people he/she encounters according to the stereotyped patterns may be symptoms of the emotional exhaustion. Depersonalization which is the other dimension or phase is defined by negative, flippant attitudes and emotions of the employee against people around his/her or people he/she provides service. The individual who falls into syndrome may think that he/she occupies place unnecessarily in the life of person or people he/she provides service; he/she may sincerely desire that people go out his/her life and leave his/her alone. Negative mentality he/she developed about others may cause negative thoughts about him/her and this individual may judge over himself/herself "failed" by mostly feeling himself/herself as guilty due to this thought and wrong behaviors. At this point, reduced personal accomplishment feeling which the third phase of burnout is reveals. Individuals feel dissatisfaction with the thought of being unsuccessful at their works and turn to activities out of the work as a result of reduced personal accomplishment feeling [12]. Such persons, who think that they do not improve in their works even they regress, feel guilty and loss their self-respect and thus, they fall into depression by believing that their effort will not serve the purpose.

It is possible to find many researches on burnout in the literature. Studies such as Aiken et al. [13] conducted their study on work satisfaction, burnout and intent to leave workforce in 5 countries (United States, Canada, United Kingdom, Scotland and Germany), 711 hospitals and 43329 nurses; Dall'Ora et al. [14]'s study measuring the effect of working hours on job satisfaction and exhaustion of nurses working in 12 European countries; and Tarcan et al. [15]' study revealing the relationship between job satisfaction and burnout can be monitored in the literature. When outcomes of burnout are examined, adverse outcomes such as work neglectation, increase in quitting tendency, deterioration in the nature of service, absenteeism without permission, tendency for extension of leave through report and similar ways at the end of leave, breakdown in human

correlations at work and out of the work and dissonance tendency, withdrawal tendency from the spouse and family members, reduced work performance, job dissatisfaction, unjust becoming sick tendencies, increase in injuries and occupational accidents at work [16,17,18,19,20].

2.2 Intrapreneurship

The concept of intrapreneurship was firstly used by Pinchot in 1985. The author defined the intrapreneurship as using the frame of mind, behaviors and qualifications which independent entrepreneurs used for establishing and developing the business within an organization which maintains its activities [3].

Intrapreneurship may be shortly defined as "entrepreneurship within the existing or available organization (business)". Antoncic and Hisrich [21] show in a study he conducted that intrapreneurship concept may be defined in various forms. These definitions are as follows; "period in which individuals within the existing organization watch for opportunities independently from the existing resources they control", "developing new works and abandoning the old habits in order to take the opportunities", "entrepreneurship thought and soul within the existing organization" and "creating new organizations by an operating organization or encouraging innovation and novelty within this organization". Researcher Zahra [22] defines the intrapreneurship and the concept of corporate entrepreneurship she used in the same meaning as innovations in organization, department, function and project levels, products and periods for the purpose of improving competition position and financial performance of an existing organization and formal and informal activities aiming to create new works through market growth.

In other words, intrapreneurship is acting like a classical entrepreneur within a large organization operating currently or the work of incenting to behave in such way. Intrapreneurship which is also expressed as corporate entrepreneurship aims to mobilize and revive the existing organization through taking risk, innovation and active competition behaviors, entrepreneurial activities leading to create a new enterprise within the existing organization, to renew the main idea of the organization and to transform the organization [23].

An intrapreneur is described as an executive or worker who sees a need and exerts for creating a new thing in order to meet that need [24] or an organization personnel [25,26] who questions, changes or rejects the idea and practices already accepted for making innovation in any subject [27].

It is possible to encounter with many different definitions related with intrapreneurship in the literature. For instance, intrapreneurs are described as "employees who see any need and create a new thing for meeting that need" in a definition [24]. In another definition, it is stated that intrapreneurs are "creative thinkers who change or reject the already accepted ideas in order to make innovation in any subject" [25]. As is seen, there are cases of creating the change, making innovation and not accepting the status quo in a sense in the definition of entrepreneurship [27].

Some studies conducted in this field address that intrapreneur individuals have unique characteristics [26,28,29,30] and these individuals bear many different personality traits. When such traits are examined in depth, it is stated that of these traits, innovativeness, taking risk and focusing on opportunities are outstanding [31,32] and the said traits are discussed as sub-dimensions of intrapreneurship [4]. It has been seen that in the study examining the relationship between motivation and innovation in the health sector also the workers' motivation has increased who are performing creative and innovative activities [33]. In the study by [34] it has been identified that there is a positive relation between dedication to work and internal entrepreneurship. In another study by [35] it has been identified that strengthening the staff has an effect on internal entrepreneurship.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Aim of the Research

It may be expected that effect of the burnout which is a negative, undesired process associated with stress on the intrapreneurship is also negative. In this study identifying the relation between burnout and intrapreneurship was aimed. Additionally, the aim was to reveal if there was a significant difference between the demographic features and burnout and intrapreneurship. In accordance with this purpose the problem question was identified as "Has the burnout that the employees come through effect their intrapreneurship behaviors.

3.2 Methodology

The sampling of this research conducted for determining the situation is consisted of employees working in the position of nurse in Ankara X State Hospital. Convenience sampling method was selected in determination of sampling in the research. Questionnaire method, five point Likert scale was used in collection of data. Number of nurse working in the related state hospital as of May 2016 was found as 169. The useable 99 question forms collected from the participants of the research were included into the scope of the research. When population size is taken as 1000, 88 samplings are accepted adequate in alpha 0.05, ± 7.08 margin of error. It is acceptable that sampling number in the research is adequate for representing the population.

The scale whose validity and reliability study were performed by [10] in Turkey is consisted of 22 questions having 5-step answer options in each one. It has three sub-dimensions as emotional exhaustion, personal accomplishment and depersonalization [7]. Emotional exhaustion and depersonalization dimensions have negative answers, personal accomplishment has positive answers. Points are calculated separately for each sub-scale. Since there is no cutting value for the points obtained from sub-scales, a distinction cannot be done in such a way that there is or not burnout. The scale which was developed by [7] and used in the measurement of burnout level in individuals is called as "Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI)". Maslach and Jackson developed this scale by considering occupational groups serving to people, they argued that burnout is a special problem concerning with these occupations. Thus, scale has been frequently used in researches conducted over human resources in the healthcare sector. Even though sub-dimensions of burnout scale are relevant, they are different concepts from each other. Therefore, it is not possible to get a total burnout point while making assessment with the scale. Each sub-dimension should be assessed and interpreted separately. As burnout increases, point of emotional exhaustion and depersonalization sub-dimensions increase and personal accomplishment point decreases [7,36].

The scale of the research called "How about measuring intrapreneurship" developed by [37] was used. The required permission for the use of original scale was obtained from through e-mail.

The permission required for the use of Turkish form of the scale was obtained from Mehmet Kiziloglu, Lecturer, Kale Vocational College, Pamukkale University who assessed the reliability of the whole original scale and sub-dimensions after having translated into Turkish and found the scale as valid and reliable (excluding 11 questions) [38].

The scale is consisted of seven sub-dimensions. All dimensions of the scale were created according to 5-point Likert scale. Accordingly, answers given to the statements in the scale are expressed respectively as follows; I never agree "1", I do not agree "2", I am hesitant "3", I agree "4", I definitely agree "5".

"Management and Organization Incentive" in the first dimension of the scale was tried to be measured with 7 questions, "Individual Motivation" in the second dimension with 5 questions, "Transparency and Clarity" in the third dimension with 5 questions and "Individual Competency" in the fourth dimension with 2 questions, "Constructive Business Network" in the fifth dimension with 3 questions, "Incentive for Innovation" in the sixth dimension with 3 questions and "Improvement" in the seventh dimension with 3 questions.

Alpha reliability value calculated for the burnout scale questionnaire was found as 0.83. Accordingly, the burnout scale may be described as reliable ($\alpha > 0.80$). Alpha value 0.947 calculated for the scale is adequate for the reliability of the questionnaire (0.80). When the whole questionnaire was considered, the problem of inadequate reliability degree ($\alpha < 0.80$) encountered in some sub-factors which the questionnaire is divided, disappeared.

3.3 Research Hypotheses

In line with the aim of the research, questions seeking answer and the developed research model are given below.

- H1₀:** There is no significant difference by the gender in mean scores of burnout.
- H1₁:** There is significant difference by the gender in mean scores of burnout.
- H2₀:** There is no significant difference by the gender in mean scores of intrapreneurship.
- H2₁:** There is significant difference by the gender in mean scores of intrapreneurship.

- H3₀:** Mean scores obtained in burnout do not differ by the educational status.
- H3₁:** Mean scores obtained in burnout differ by the educational status.
- H4₀:** Mean scores obtained in intrapreneurship do not differ by the educational level.
- H4₁:** Mean scores obtained in intrapreneurship differ by the educational level.
- H5₀:** Mean scores obtained in the burnout do not differ by the occupational experience.
- H5₁:** Mean scores obtained in the burnout differ by the occupational experience.
- H6₀:** Mean scores obtained in intrapreneurship do not differ by the occupational experience.
- H6₁:** Mean scores obtained in intrapreneurship differ by the occupational experience.
- H7₀:** There is a negative correlation between burnout which employee experienced and intrapreneurship tendency.
- H7₁:** There is a positive correlation between burnout which employee experienced and intrapreneurship tendency.
- H8₀:** There is a negative correlation between "emotional exhaustion" that is a sub-dimension of burnout concept and intrapreneurship tendency of the working personnel.
- H8₁:** There is a positive correlation between "emotional exhaustion" that is a sub-dimension of burnout concept and intrapreneurship tendency of the working personnel.
- H9₀:** There is a negative correlation between "personal accomplishment" that is a sub-dimension of burnout concept and intrapreneurship tendency of the working personnel.
- H9₁:** There is a positive correlation between "personal accomplishment" that is a sub-dimension of burnout concept and intrapreneurship tendency of the working personnel.
- H10₀:** There is a negative correlation between "depersonalization" that is a sub-dimension of burnout concept and intrapreneurship tendency of the working personnel.
- H10₁:** There is a positive correlation between "depersonalization" that is a sub-dimension of burnout concept and intrapreneurship tendency of the working personnel.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

86 (%86,9) of the personnel participated into the research are female, 13 (%13,1) of whom are

male. When age distribution of participants of questionnaire is examined, there are 25 (%25,2) participants in 20-30 age interval, 57 (%57,6) participants in 31-40 age interval, 16 (%16,2) participants in 41-50 age interval and 1 (%1,0) participant in the age interval of 51 and above. 33 (%33,3) people are associate degree graduates, 45 (%45,5) are bachelor's degree graduates, 11 (%11,1) are master's degree graduates and 10 (%10,1) are doctorate degree graduates. 79 (%79,8) of 99 participants are married, 20 (%20,2) participants are single. There are 15 (%15,2) participants in 1-5 years of total working period, 21 (%21,2) participants in 6-10 years, 22 (%22,2) participants in 11-15 years and 27 (%27,3) participants in 16-20 years, 14 (%14,1) participants of 21 and above. 23 (%23,2) participants were found in 0-7 years of occupational field experience, 35 (%35,4) participants in 8-15 years' interval, 26 (%26,3) participants in 16-20 years' interval, 15 (%15,1) participants in years' interval of 21 and above.

Table 1. Findings related to demographic characteristics

Variables		N	%
Gender	Female	86	86,9
	Male	13	13,1
Age	20-30	25	25,2
	31-40	57	57,6
	41-50	16	16,2
	At and above 51	1	1,0
Education	Associate Degree	33	33,3
	Undergraduate	45	45,5
	Graduate	11	11,1
	PHD	10	10,1
Marital status	Single	20	20,2
	Married	79	79,8
Time of work	1-5 years	15	15,2
	6-10 years	21	21,2
	11-15 years	22	22,2
	16-20 years	27	27,3
	21 years and more	14	14,1
Occupational experience	0-7 years	23	23,2
	8-15 years	35	35,4
	16-20 years	26	26,3
	21 years and more	15	15,1

4.1 Testing of Hypotheses

4.1.1 Testing the gender and burnout relation hypothesis

- H1₀:** There is no significant difference by the gender in mean scores of burnout.
- H1₁:** There is significant difference by the gender in mean scores of burnout.

4.1.2 Testing the gender and intrapreneurship relation hypothesis

- H2₀:** There is no significant difference by the gender in mean scores of intrapreneurship.
- H2₁:** There is significant difference by the gender in mean scores of intrapreneurship.

4.1.3 Testing the education level and burnout relation hypothesis

- H3₀:** Mean scores obtained in burnout do not differ by the educational status.
- H3₁:** Mean scores obtained in burnout differ by the educational status.

4.1.4 Testing the education level and intrapreneurship relation hypothesis

- H4₀:** Mean scores obtained in intrapreneurship do not differ by the educational level.
- H4₁:** Mean scores obtained in intrapreneurship differ by the educational level.

4.1.5 Testing the professional experience and burnout relation hypothesis

- H5₀:** Mean scores obtained in the burnout do not differ by the occupational experience.
- H5₁:** Mean scores obtained in the burnout differ by the occupational experience.

4.1.6 Testing the professional experience and intrapreneurship relation hypothesis

- H6₀:** Mean scores obtained in intrapreneurship do not differ by the occupational experience.
- H6₁:** Mean scores obtained in intrapreneurship differ by the occupational experience.

Results obtained from the calculation of correlation between the burnout and intrapreneurship with Sperman Correlation Analysis is presented in the Table 8. Accordingly, when the general means are considered, it is seen that there is a negative and weak ($r = -0.273$) correlation between intrapreneurship and burnout. This result means that there is a reverse correlation between intrapreneurship and burnout, an increase to be experienced in the burnout score will lead to decrease in intrapreneurship. According to the results hypothesizes H7₀, H8₀, H9₀, H10₀ have been accepted.

Table 2. Relation between gender and burnout

Relation between gender and burnout	Levene's test		T-Test						
	F	Sig.	t	df	p	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence interval of the difference	
								Lower	Upper
Equal variances assumed	,189	,665	-,460	97	,647	-,07989	,17368	-,42460	,26482
Equal variances not assumed			-,489	16,578	,631	-,07989	,16345	-,42540	,26562

$p < 0.05$; Since p value we obtained is $0.647 > 0.05$, H_{10} negation hypothesis cannot be rejected. In this case, we can say that the mean score obtained in burnout does not differ by the gender

Table 3. Gender and intrapreneurship relation

Gender and intrapreneurship relation	Levene's test		T-test						
	F	Sig.	t	df	p	Mean difference	Std. error difference	95% Confidence interval of the difference	
								Lower	Upper
Equal variances assumed	,000	,983	,946	97	,347	,18879	,19966	-,20749	,58507
Equal variances not assumed			,929	15,665	,367	,18879	,20319	-,24270	,62028

$p < 0.05$; Since p value we obtained is $0.347 > 0.05$, H_{20} negation hypothesis cannot be rejected. In this case, we can say that the mean score obtained in intrapreneurship does not differ by the gender

Table 4. Education level and burnout relation

	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	p
Between groups	1,741	3	,580	1,757	,161
Within groups	31,375	95	,330		
Total	33,116	98			

$p < 0.05$; Since p value we obtained is $0.161 > 0.05$, H_{30} negation hypothesis cannot be rejected. In this case, we can say that the mean score obtained in burnout does not differ by the educational status

Table 5. Education level and intrapreneurship relation

	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	p
Between groups	2,224	3	,741	1,683	,176
Within groups	41,848	95	,441		
Total	44,072	98			

$p < 0.05$; Since p value we obtained is $0.176 > 0.05$, H_{40} negation hypothesis cannot be rejected. In this case, we can say that the mean score obtained in intrapreneurship does not differ by the educational status

Table 6. Professional experience and burnout relation

	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	p
Between groups	2,086	3	,695	2,129	,102
Within groups	31,030	95	,327		
Total	33,116	98			

$p < 0.05$; Since p value we obtained is $0.102 > 0.05$, H_{50} negation hypothesis cannot be rejected. In this case, we can say that the mean score obtained in burnout does not differ by the occupational experience

Table 7. Professional experience and intrapreneurship relation

	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	p
Between groups	2,063	3	,688	1,555	,205
Within groups	42,009	95	,442		
Total	44,072	98			

$p < 0.05$; Since p value we obtained is $0.205 > 0.05$, H_0 negation hypothesis cannot be rejected. In this case, we can say that the mean score obtained in intrapreneurship does not differ by the occupational experience

Table 8. Burnout and intrapreneurship relation

	I	I_F1	I_F2	I_F3	I_F4	I_F5	I_F6	I_F7	B	B_EE	B_PA	B_D
I	1											
I_F1	,869	1										
I_F2	,894	,787	1									
I_F3	,740	,506	,562	1								
I_F4	,734	,589	,529	,550	1							
I_F5	,746	,501	,588	,637	,651	1						
I_F6	,694	,469	,569	,408	,655	,618	1					
I_F7	,723	,533	,582	,534	,500	,568	,562	1				
B	-,273	-,221	-,285	-,128	-,345	-,222	-,283	-,129	1			
B_EE	-,296	-,240	-,300	-,158	-,370	-,202	-,284	-,158	,880	1		
B_PA	-,377	-,343	-,400	-,199	-,357	-,244	-,277	-,173	,762	,580	1	
B_D	-,027	,013	-,049	,026	-,102	-,099	-,147	,014	,790	,546	,445	1

I: Intrapreneurship B: Burnout EE: Emotional Exhaustion PA: Personal Accomplishment D: Depersonalization
F: Factor

Table 9. Regression analysis between burnout and internal entrepreneurship

Independent variables	B	Beta	t	p	R	R ²	DeltaR ²	F	p
Constant	4.148		11.162	0.000	0.264	0.070	0.060	7.276	0.008
Burnout	-0.305	-0.264	-2.697	0.008					

Dependent Variable: Entrepreneurship

When the results from simple linear regression analysis are examined, it has been found that burnout is important in explaining internal entrepreneurship ($p=0.008 < 0.05$). When Beta value is examined, it can be said that the effect of burnout is negative. The model can explain about 6% ($\Delta R^2 = 0.060$) of total variation (variance) with this state.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The burnout concept which is defined together with emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and reduced personal accomplishment dimensions may affect intrapreneurship attitudes negatively in many respects in the business life in our present day. As mentioned in the above, we confront the entrepreneurship as a period requiring a vigorous effort and energy. If an individual who is able to produce new behavior or solution almost in any matter, to take risk if

required or assesses the emerging opportunities quickly, experiences emotional exhaustion, depersonalization or reduced personal accomplishment feeling, this will affect his/her entrepreneurial behaviors negatively [39].

In this research, correlation between burnout levels and intrapreneurship attitudes was searched in its all levels. The sampling of this research is consisted of employees working in the position of nurse in Ankara X State Hospital. Convenience sampling method was selected in determination of sampling in the research and questionnaire method and 5-point Likert scale were used in collection of data.

Questions determined by the burnout and intrapreneurship scales were implemented to Likert scale, sampling of the research. According to the research findings, when depersonalization feeling of the burnout dimensions increases, decrease in intrapreneurship tendency of the

individual is seen and when emotional exhaustion increases, again decrease in intrapreneurship tendency is seen. It is seen that when personal accomplishment feeling decreases, intrapreneurship tendency increases. Aiken and Slonae with Aiken, Slonae and Lake [40,41] have shown that burnout and job satisfaction are particularly important for nurses in their study on nurses. Aiken et al. [13] found that the highest job dissatisfaction in the study of job satisfaction, burnout and job separation intentions on 711 hospitals and 43329 nurses in 5 countries (United States, Canada, UK, Scotland and Germany) was lowest in the United States It turns out he was in Germany. Dall'Ora et al. [14] found that 12 hours long working hours of nurses working in 12 European countries lead to job dissatisfaction and burnout in their study measuring the effects of work hours on job satisfaction and burnout. Again, in the literature, Tarcan et al. [15] found that there is a significant relationship between job satisfaction and burnout in their study that reveals the relationship between job satisfaction and burnout. Studies in the literature are supporting our study.

According to the results of the study, because the entrepreneurship behavior of the nurses is directly related to the level of burnout, it is clear that managers need to reduce, control and take precautions for the burnout levels of the nurses. It will be possible to increase entrepreneurship skills and use their creativity while the burnout of the nurses is reducing. However, providing the necessary in-service training, offering promotional opportunities, flexible working hours and working environment increase job satisfaction and reduce burnout [42,43]. For this reason, dealing with these factors will also reduce burnout.

Since the study is limited with only one state hospital, results do not give precise information. It will be continued to search by enlarging the population in the future.

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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